

5G CITY

Grant Agreement No.761508 5GCITY/H2020-ICT-2016-2017/H2020-ICT-2016-2

D6.1 Project Dissemination and Communication Plan

Dissemination Level	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
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Grant Agreement no: 761508	Project Acronym: 5G CITY	Project title: 5G CITY
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Lead Beneficiary:	Document version: V1.0
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Work package: WP6 5GCity Dissemination, Exploitation, and Standardization

Deliverable title: D6.1 Project Dissemination and communication plan
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Start date of the project: 01.06.2017 (duration 30 months)	Contractual delivery date: 6 Month	Actual delivery date: 30.11.2017
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Change History

Version	Date	Partners	Description/Comments
01	13-10-17	i2CAT	TOC
02	27-10-17	i2CAT	First draft
03	17-11-17	All	Feedback for section4
04-07	22-11-17	I2cat	General revisions
09	29-11-17	I2cat	Final version

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5GCITY has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761508. The content of this deliverable does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information and views expressed in the deliverable lies entirely with the author(s).

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Executive Summary

5GCITY consortium recognizes the importance of giving visibility to the results of the projects funded by the H2020 program. This deliverable provides an exhaustive dissemination plan that will be used as guideline during the project and structures a first set of actions that will be implemented during the project. The ultimate objective of this plan is to coordinate the effort of the partners and to implement a coherent and uniform message to the different stakeholders.

The deliverable is divided in five sections. In the first one we provide a general introduction to the document and identify the stakeholders to whom address the outputs of the project. In the second one, we define the communication tools that will be used ensuring a homogenous output and an appropriate dissemination of the messages. In section three, we identify the different events that will be used to raise awareness of the activities developed in 5GCITY. The responsibility of each partner in this events is defined in section four. This section provides more elaborative dissemination plan from each partner on how they plan to implement the outlines already included in the DoA. In the last section, the actions included in this plan are linked with the KPI used to measure the advances of the project and how the outputs should be reported to the Project Coordinator (PC).

The dissemination and communication plan will be updated and corrected every year of the project in deliverables D6.3 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Standardization Activities M12, D6.4 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Standardization Activities M24. The dissemination effort of the project is complemented by the outputs defined in the Data Management Plan (D1.2 M6) where the consortium defines what data outputs will be shared.

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

The 5GCity Dissemination Plan document describes the tools and strategies to be used by the 5GCity project, to raise awareness about the research results achieved by the project, detailing the planned activities to be used for dissemination.

This document aims to coordinate and plan the dissemination activities both at consortium and partner level. Partners will contribute to the dissemination activities via the most appropriate methods according to their expertise. It is expected that academic partners and research institutes are expected to put more emphasis and time into journal publications and conference presentations, while industrial partners will rather focus on standardization and presentations towards potential users and stakeholders, which enable the project to get feedback on the achieved outcomes.

1.2. Stakeholders identification

Some outputs of the 5GCITY project related with the city pilots will reach a wide audience as city pilots will have broad dissemination through the media. Leaving this specific impact, the main stakeholders will be the European and global research groups, organizations and companies linked to the technological development and industrial, academic and scientific communities. To raise the awareness in these groups, 5GCity will make presentations and demonstrations of project results and experiences, so that telecom stakeholders and also other communities across Europe will benefit from the knowledge sharing. In addition, the project will also aim to inform to citizens and policy makers from the local and regional governments.

Figure 1: Project stakeholders

2. Communication tools

2.1. Project Website

5GCity's website will have a major role in dissemination & communication activities. At the beginning of project an eye-catching website has been launched.

All the information about the project's activities (past, on-going, upcoming), developments, and results will be accessible from the 5GCity website. The 5GCity site will also offer both News and Blog sections. All public dissemination material (presentations, flyers, press releases, etc.), about the project, will be made publicly available through the project's website. These will all be licensed via a Creative Commons license (likely the "CC BY" license) for maximum dissemination and use of licensed presentations.

5GCity's website will contain also links to other relevant sites, from projects point of view, as for example the code repository, or links to zenodo webpage where the project publications will be stored.

The URL for 5GCity website is the following: <http://www.5gcity.eu/>

In order to ensure the sustainability of the project results, the web site will be available a minimum of two years after project's end.

Figure 2: Project Website

2.2. Social Media

The 5GCity [Twitter](#) account will help when disseminating news, events and achievements from the project, but won't be the only way. 5GCity's social presence will also extend to [Linkedin](#), [YouTube](#),

Figure 3: 5GCity twitter

Figure 4: 5GCity LinkedIn Group Page

Figure 5: 5GCity YouTube Channel

2.3. Press Releases

One of the mechanism to raise public awareness and to reach the general public will be through the press releases. They will be periodically issued, and all the partners will be invited to make diffusion through their web sites to make impact on their local/regional media.

ACCELLERAN	http://www.acceleran.com/the-5gcity-project-has-been-launched/
VOSYS	http://www.virtualopensystems.com/en/research/innovation-projects/edge-computing-5gcity/
INCITES	http://www.incites.eu/5GCity-project-press-release/
BTV	http://beteve.cat/projecte-5gcity-5g-barcelona-beteve-i2cat/(for some reason doesn't open from here)
	https://btv.playty.com/player#/video?autoplay=1&id=200617MH5g
INCITES	http://www.incites.eu/5GCity-project-press-release/

These press releases had an impact in local press fostering the debate about the implementation of 5G.

Press	Name	Title	Link
Press	EIPuntAvui	Catalunya és la referència europea de la recerca en 5G	http://www.elpuntavui.cat/societat/article/5-societat/1147448-catalunya-es-la-referencia-europea-de-la-recerca-en-5g.html
Radio	RAC1	El Món a RAC1: Tecnologies digitals avançades i posicionament en 5G	http://www.rac1.cat/a-la-carta/detail/a6f29e91-48a8-4ed3-bf80-64a194f51513
Radio	LaCope Ràdio	Tecnologies presentades a la innovation zone per i2CAT	
TV	Betevé	Barcelona i betevé, banc de proves de la tecnologia 5G	http://beteve.cat/projecte-5gcity-5g-barcelona-beteve-i2cat/
Press	EIPuntAvui - Suplement dominical	Fondre el temps a les xarxes	http://www.elpuntavui.cat/economia/article/18-economia/1162477-fondre-el-temps-a-les-xarxes.html
Press	Diari Ara	Una 5G més catalana que espanyola?	http://m.ara.cat/media/mes-catalana-que-espanyola_0_1817818270.html
Press	El País	Barcelona se posiciona como laboratorio para desarrollar el 5G	http://economia.elpais.com/economia/2017/06/20/actualidad/1497960125_295536.html
Press	El Mundo	La futura red 5G se testa en Barcelona	http://www.elmundo.es/economia/innovadores/2017/06/27/5952379be2704e6e118b4579.html
Press	SPACEREF	SES and SaT5G to Spearhead Development of Ubiquitous 5G Network Capabilities	http://www.spaceref.com/news/viewpr.html?pid=51132
TV	Terrícoles Betevé	Terrícoles: Sergi Figuerola, director tècnic Fundació i2Cat	http://beteve.cat/clip/terricoles-sergi-figuerola/
Press	Economiad hoy	La agenda de BIT EXPERIENCE 2017 se centrará en 4K – HDR – 5G - OTT/IP – eSports	http://www.economiadehoy.es/noticia/21938/tecnologia/la-agenda-de-bit-experience-2017-se-centrara-en-4k--hdr--5g---ott/ip--esports.html
Press	Panorama Audiovisual	El 5G abrirá una nueva frontera para el audiovisual	https://www.panoramaaudiovisual.com/2017/10/04/el-5g-abrira-una-nueva-frontera/

2.4. Project Logo

The project logo was designed from the beginning of the project to establish the corporate image for the 5GCity project. The chosen logo will be used in the website, in presentations, document templates, deliverables and all other promotional material. The project logo is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 6: 5GCity logo

2.5. Document templates

In order to have a more coherent view of the 5GCity outcomes, a set of templates are available to be used for presentations and deliverables. These templates are available to the whole consortium via the project communication portal in confluence under the Templates & Logos section.

Figure 7: Deliverable document template

Figure 8: Presentation Template

2.6. Promotional Material

To inform the public when organizing or participating in events, leaflets, brochures and posters are key elements to disseminate information about the project. Leaflets will be distributed on the events where 5GCity project will be present.

A first version of a leaflet has been created already in the initial phase of the project. It provides quick facts about project: partners, objectives, reference architecture, etc. This version of the leaflet was first circulated in the 2017 EuCNC event that took place in Oulu from June the 12th to the 15th, 2017. The leaflet will be updated during the second period of the project, illustrating the most important achievements.

Attached here are the two sides of the leaflet:

Figure 9: Outer side of the 5GCity promotional leaflet

Figure 10: Inner side of the 5GCity promotional leaflet

3. Dissemination activities

3.1. Open Source Contributions

5GCity plans to participate in a number of open source communities with the aim to possible source code contribution in accordance with the results of the project aligned with the necessities of the targeted open source communities. For instance, during the second year NEC is planning to present the Unicore tool to the XEN community of the Linux Foundation.

The communities identified as potential stake holders where the results of the project could have a bigger impact are the following:

- KVM community
- QEMU developers' community
- Linux Foundation (XEN community)
- Open Data Plane (ODP) project
- OPNFV project
- Contributions to ETSI OSM

3.2. City Pilots

One of the key elements of the project are five pilots or proofs of concept that will be produced during the lifetime of the project. These will be demonstrated on city test beds, and will be used as a platform for experimentation, becoming an excellent opportunity for dissemination purposes. In deliverable D2.1 (5GCity System Requirements and Use Cases M7) each of the use cases are described in detail. Below we summarize the main features of each one

1. Unauthorized waste dumping prevention (smart city pilot, Lucca): This pilot will monitor through video surveillance unauthorized dumping of waste materials, shortening the time between the suspected violation and response.
2. Neutral host pilot (telecom pilot, Lucca, Barcelona, Bristol). The objective of this pilot is allowing different operators or service providers to engage in new business models based on neutral host concept.
3. Video acquisition and edge/cloud production (media pilot, Barcelona, Bristol). This pilot aims to develop tools capable of acquiring and transmitting high quality video in a 5G context.
4. UHD video distribution (media pilot, Bristol, Lucca). This pilot aims to provide end-users through their technological platforms additional UHD content (historical, cultural...) from the city.
5. Mobile backpack media unit (media pilot, Barcelona). The objective of this pilot is to increase the performance of the backup TV transmission units, reducing latency and connection.

3.3. Contributions to Standards

5GCity sits at crossroads between the Cloud, MEC, and 5G worlds and, consequently, will target dissemination in all three domains. Research partners in the 5GCity consortium have the possibility to influence different standards by contributing to those, with inputs obtained from the results and

experimentation done over the test beds prepared for 5GCity. The most favorable standard communities where to make an impact, in line with the research goals of the project, are the following:

- The OpenFog consortium: The 5GCity consortium has some partners who are active members in the OpenFog community. They will target to disseminate findings of the 5GCity project, so that they are considered when defining the OpenFog architecture. At the same time, they will contribute back to the 5GCity architecture, in order for the project to benefit from the standards defined at the OpenFog consortium.
- The ETSI NFV consortium: Some of the partners in the 5GCity consortium are following closely the specifications proposed by ETSI NFV ISG (<http://www.etsi.org/technologies-clusters/technologies/nfv>). The goal is to disseminate 5GCity vision of NFV in the ETSI NFV ISG and also ensure 5GCity planned development are aligned with ETSI NFV ISG recommendations.
- Additionally, ETSI MEC (mobile edge computing) will be one of the standardization group targets of this project.
- Other standards will be analyzed in WP6 standardization task.

3.4. Industry Events

In order for 5GCity to have a bigger impact on the industry, it is very important to make itself visible by organizing workshops at national / international level about 5G and edge technologies. This provides the consortium the opportunity to highlight project results in the industry.

In consequence, the project aims to be present and to participate in the most relevant world-wide events, such as:

- Mobile World Congress
- Smart Cities World Congress
- Industrial IoT World Congress
- Fog computing Expo
- ITS World Congress
- TV Markets, European Digital Forum, UltraHD 4K Summit

Some of the events on 5GCity radar include: Smart City Expo 17, 18 & 19, MWC 18 & 19, 5GWorld, etc.

3.5. Publications and Posters

5GCity will expand its reach by producing research publications for top-tier conferences and journals such as SIGCOMM, CoNEXT, USENIX ATC, NSDI, INFOCOM, HotCloud, ACM CCR, IEEE ComMag, CloudNet, NetCloud, etc.). These publications will target different audiences as for example the Industry Community, the Scientific Community or just the general public attending to EU organized Events. The types of documents in each of the segments are as follows:

- Industry related (SCWE, MWC, etc.): Publications of White papers, magazines, technology roadmaps, and industry-led journals
- Scientific community (IEEE ICC, IEEE Globecom, IEEE NFV/SDN, etc.): Publication of scientific results in high-impact journals and leading conferences
- EU events (e.g., EuCNC, etc.): Presentation of 5GCity results, research and innovation activities, booth exhibition and demo set ups

Posters will be created during project's lifetime. At the beginning posters will include key information related to the project. Later versions will be enhanced with research results and achievements of the project. The posters will be used in conferences, workshops and other events in order to increase awareness about the objectives and outcomes achieved by the project.

In the following sub-sections, we summarize the internal procedures to address the publications in academic journals. We make emphasis on the necessity of publishing in open journals (green option by default and gold option will be evaluated for high impact papers) and on the necessity of acknowledging the funding body (EC)

3.5.1. Open Access Policy

Open access (OA) refers to the practice of providing, free of charge to any user, online access to: all peer-reviewed scientific information and all the research data.

In particular, the 5GCity project must:

(a) As soon as possible and at the latest on publication date, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

(b) Ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:

- On publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher,
- Or within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) Ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

In 5GCity, to ensure open access, it has been agreed to use [OpenAIRE \(OpenAIRE:5GCity\)](#) to link different [Zenodo](#) repositories, containing the stored research publications. More details on which data will be made public are provided on D1.2 Project Innovation Strategy and DMP.

3.5.2. Publication Procedure

As defined in the article 8.4 of the CA 20 calendar days prior to any publication notice must be given to the other parties. Objections must be raised in writing at least 10 days after the receipt of the notice. When a publication gets reviewed and approved, it will be uploaded to Confluence and it will be shared with the whole consortium.

3.5.3. Acknowledgement

All the publications, conference proceedings, presentations on workshops, seminars, press releases or public events must take into account the following rule:

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) Display the EU emblem and
- (b) Include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761508”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

3.6. Blog

To make the website a reference point in the development of 5G technologies, aside from constantly updating the news section in the web, a blog will be monthly posted by the different partners on topics related to the project. In this blog, the partners will share relevant aspects of their involvement of the project.

The initial commitment of the partners of the consortium it is seen below

Table 1: Responsible for blog contribution

Date	Month	partner
Jan-18	8	I2CAT
Feb-18	9	NEC
Mar-18	10	VOSYS
Apr-18	11	PRISMTECH
May-18	12	RETEVISION I
Jun-18	13	UNIVBRIS
Sep-18	16	BIO
Oct-18	17	NXW
Nov-18	18	COMUNE DI LUCCA
Dec-18	19	ITL
Jan-19	20	IMI BCN
Feb-19	21	MOG
Mar-19	22	WI3
Apr-19	23	RAI
May-19	24	Ubiwhere
Jun-19	25	BTV
Jul-19	26	INCITES
Sep-19	28	Accelleran
Oct-19	29	CoDi
Nov-19	30	i2cat

3.7. Newsletters

Newsletters will be used to periodically highlight the achievements from the project and at the same time report different dissemination activities (papers published, participation in other events). The newsletters will be published from month 9th onwards and with a quarterly Frequency. These newsletters will include the

relevant information from last three months, including: contributions in workshops and congress, publications related to the project, dissemination actions and links to the contents of the blog posts.

3.8. Hackathons

Hackathons will help to both disseminate by presenting and open up the project infrastructure to the communities, and to test the maturity of the developed solution. Two hackathons will be organized during the middle phases of the project. First one will be organized by IMI in Barcelona after the first release. A second hackaton is expected to be organized at NEC based on UNICORE, although this decision will depend on the availability of the other partners and the technical evolution of the project.

3.9. Impact in Academia

Aside from the impact that will have in the academia through the research papers, we have identified two further impacts: UNIVBRIS will aim to include 5GCity's results into its PhD and Masters programs and in NEC a PhD Student is developing a Thesis on Unicore related with the project.

3.10. Workshops

At least two workshops will be organized during the final phases of the project. One workshop for Smart Cities has been already identified and will be hosted by Retevision HQ in Barcelona. The institution for the second workshop will be decided at later phases and according to evolution of the project.

3.11. Events

The consortium has defined different events where they ought to contribute to disseminate the project results. A first non-exhaustive list, sorted in chronological order can be find below. This list will be regularly updated when new targets are identified and new outputs are generated.

Table 2 : Partners participating in different events

Timeline	Partner	Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
Jun-17	i2cat	EUCNC-17	Invited talk for presenting the project. "A distributed cloud & radio platform for 5G neutral hosts" Sergi Figuerola (I2cat)	https://5g-ppp.eu/eucnc-2017-oulu-presentations/

Jun-17	RAI /CODI	14th European Digital Forum	5G Dedicated Session: '5G CITY & A NEW GREEN BROADCASTING' and speaking slot during the event, media promotion, 5GCity logo/brand visibility, social promotion, dissemination	http://www.comunicaredigitale.it/en/agenda-lucca-2017/
Jun-17	INCITES	Production of a video highlighting the 5G City concept		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VKcF0pkDiX8&pbjreload=10
Oct-17	i2cat	BiTExperience 2017	Invited project presentation and Panel discussion on "5G Y LA NUEVA FRONTERA AUDIOVISUAL Y MULTIMEDIA. 5GMEDIA Y 5G CITY, ADELANTÁNDOSE AL FUTURO"	http://www.ifema.es/bitexperience_06/Prensa/NotasdePrensa/INS_094523_06
Oct-17	UBIWHERE	Visions for Future Communications Summit	Invited to talk about "The Global Internet of the Future" and Ubiwhere's current and future R&I	https://futurecomresearch.eu
Sep-17	H3G	Fireworks: Amsterdam Meeting # 52 (Sep 27nd-28t)	Activities Project presentation	Presentation @ Fireworks board
Sep-17	IMI	SESIAD (Spain Government) UNE (Standardization Bodies)	Face to face meeting	Not Available
Nov-17	XLRN, BTV, IMI, UBIWHERE, I2CAT	SMARTCITY Expo World Congress	Presentation of the project in several Booths, and invited talks	http://www.smartcityexpo.com/en/
Nov-17	Prismtech	2017 Global Mobile Broadband Forum	Invited talk	http://www.huawei.com/minisite/hwmbbf17/assert_4/files/MBB_Invitation_letter_en.pdf
Nov-17	XLRN	Smart City Expo '17 - Barcelona	Booth at the Smart City Expo, Small Cell integration in Barcelona Lamppost	Attendance, Smart City Expo 2017 in Barcelona
Nov-17	UBI	Smart City Expo '17 - Barcelona	Booth at the Smart City Expo, Smart pole concept and vision presentation.	Smart pole concept and prototype presentation. . Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) use case presentation.
Nov-17	RTV (Cellnex)	Smart City Expo '17 - Barcelona	Booth at the Smart City Expo, Project description in video world.	Attendance and presentation.

Nov-17	IMI	Smart City Expo '17 - Barcelona	Booth at the Smart City Expo	Not Available
Nov-17	UBI	Salon des Maires 2017	Small booth (Smart Lamppost) where 5GCITY's Use Cases will be quickly presented	Salon des Maires 2017
Dec-17	XLRN	Small Cell World Summit Americas San Jose 2017	Booth at the SCWS Americas 2017 with PR/panel related to 5GCity	Attendance, SCWS America 2017
Feb-18	XLRN	MWC 2018 - Barcelona	Booth at the MWC18 with PR/panel related to 5GCity	Attendance, MWC18
Feb-18	RTV (Cellnex)	MWC 2018 - Barcelona	Booth at the MWC, Project presentation. Outcomes shown in video panel.	Attendance and NH architecture showcasing, also presenting with IMI, Accelleran and i2Cat.
Feb-18	UBI	MWC 2018 - Barcelona	Probably a booth	Smart pole concept and prototype presentation. Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) use case presentation.
Feb-18	NXW	Softnetworking 2018	Submission of a paper	https://www.iaria.org/conferences/2018/SOFTNETWORKING18.html
Mar-18	INCITES	OFC	Paper submitted for presentation	Presentation (if paper is accepted)
Mar-18	UNIBRIS	5G UK Winter Festival	Presentation and dissemination by using posters and talk about 5G City project.	Not Available
Apr-18	CODI	PE/Brussels	5G Press Conference/Workshop	Not Available
May-18	CODI	BIT 2018 - Madrid	5G Media Round Table	Not Available
Jun-18	VOSYS	Interop 2018 - Tokyo	Booth and demonstration	Attendance, Interop 2018 in Tokyo
Jun-18	VOSYS	IEEE BMSB 2018 - Valencia	Technical paper presentation	Authors
Jun-18	INCITES	EuCNC	Submission of a paper or/and organization of a workshop	Attendance, presentation, organization of a workshop
Jun-18	NXW	EuCNC	Submission of a paper	Not Available
Jun-18	CODI	4th F2F 5GCity - Lucca	5GCity Consortium Meeting	Not Available
Jun-18	CODI	FED 2018 - Lucca	5G Media Keynote/Round Table/Demo Area	Not Available
Jun-18	CODI	5GWorld - London	5G Media Keynote/Round Table/Demo Area	Not Available

Jun-18	RAI	European Digital Forum and UHD 4K Summit - Lucca	Presentation and demo area	Not Available
Jun-18	UBI	EuCNC 2018	To be confirmed	Not Available
Jul-18	NEC	IEEE HPSR	Unicore Hackathon (co-hosted)	http://hpsr2018.ieee-hpsr.org/
Sep-18	MOG	IBC 2018 - Amsterdam	Booth (Use case demonstration at IBC 2018)	Attendance, IBC expo.
Sep-18	INCITES	5G Pine workshop	Submission of a paper	Presentation (if paper is accepted)
Sep-18	CODI	IBC 2018 - Amsterdam	5G Media Paper	Not Available
Sep-18	UNIBRIS	ECOC 2018	Paper submission for presentation	http://www.ecoc2018.org/
Sep-18	RAI	IBC 2018 - Amsterdam	5G Media Paper	Not Available
Oct-18	UNIBRIS	SDN NFV World Congress (NFV+SDN & Automation for 5G, Transport & Cloud)	Posters promoting 5G City preliminary results.	https://www.layer123.com/sdn-register/
Fall 2018	Lucca	POLIS annual Conference, Brussels	Booth and presentation	https://www.polisnetwork.eu
Nov-18	i2cat	Smart City Expo '18 - Barcelona	Booth at the Smart City Expo	Attendance, Smart City Expo 2018 in Barcelona
Nov-18	UBI	Smart City Expo '18 - Barcelona	Probably a booth	Attendance, Smart City Expo 2018 in Barcelona
Nov-18	RTV (Cellnex)	Smart City Expo '18 - Barcelona	Booth at the Smart City Expo, Project description in video world.	Attendance and presentation.
Nov-18	IMI	Smart City Expo '18 - Barcelona	Booth at the Smart City Expo	Not Available
Nov-18	CODI	4KSummit 2018 - Malaga	5G Media Keynote/Round Table/	Not Available
Nov-18	RAI	EBU Forecast 2018	Presentation	Not Available
Open 2018	NEC	Xen Summit	Unicore presentation (Unicore is about to become a Xen sub-project)	Not Available
Open 2018	UNIBRIS	IEEE Communication Magazine	Submit an article about 5G and MEC/FOG	Not Available
tbd	NEC	Linuxcon 2018	Unicore presentation	Not Available
tbd	NEC	Linaro conference 2018	Unicore presentation	Not Available

Feb-19	i2cat	MWC 2019 - Barcelona	Pilot demonstration at MWC 2019	Attendance, 5GCity demonstration at MWC 2019, utilizing the Barcelona pilot
Feb-19	XLRN	MWC 2019 - Barcelona	Pilot demonstration at MWC 2019	Attendance, 5GCity demonstration at MWC 2019, utilizing the Barcelona pilot
Feb-19	RTV (Cellnex)	MWC 2019 - Barcelona	Booth at the MWC, Project presentation. Outcomes shown in video panel.	Attendance and NH use case demonstration.
Mar-19	UNIBRIS	OFC 2019	Paper submission for presentation	http://www.ofcconference.org/en-us/home/?utm_source=researchbib
Apr-19	MOG	NAB 2019 - Los Angeles	Booth (Use case demonstration at NAB 2019)	Attendance, NAB expo.
Jun-19	INCITES	EuCNC	Submission of a paper or/and organization of a workshop	Attendance, presentation, organization of a workshop
Jul-19	UNIBRIS	IEEE ICTON 2019	Paper submission for presentation	Not Available
Nov-19	IMI	Smart City Expo '19 - Barcelona	Booth at the Smart City Expo	Not Available
Open 2019	UNIBRIS	IEEE/OSA Scientific Journal	Article extending all conference papers presented.	https://www.osapublishing.org
Open 2019	UNIBRIS	Open Network Foundation (ONF) standarization group	Interactions for standardization of interfaces.	https://www.opennetworking.org/events/
Open 2019	Lucca	European Committee of the regions, Brussels	Press conference and presentation	http://cor.europa.eu/en

4. Partners involvement towards the dissemination objectives

5GCity dissemination plan, describes the coordinated efforts of the consortium into achieving the dissemination goals. The following subchapters show an updated version of the partner commitment as were firstly defined in the DoA.

4.1. Fundació i2CAT

Fundació i2cat will contribute to the dissemination objectives of 5GCity by producing publications of high-quality results in international media like peer reviewed magazines and journals including special issues in selected journals as: IEEE Transactions, IEEE ComMag or TNC

i2cat will also contribute to the dissemination of the project by organizing a workshop at the Smart City Expo 2018 on 5G-based Edge Cities. The following year, during the time of the MWC 2019 and using for that the Barcelona pilot, i2cat will be organizing and hosting a 5GCity demonstration

Another way in which i2cat will help with the objectives for dissemination is by making contributions to selected open source communities. The ones that seem to align better with the objectives of 5GCity are OpenDayLight and ETSI open-source MANO. i2cat plans to make at least three contributions into those previously named communities.

Table 3: i2cat planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
Smart City Expo '18 - Barcelona	November 2018	Booth at the Smart City Expo	Attendance, Smart City Expo 2018 in Barcelona
MWC 2019 - Barcelona	February 2019	Pilot demonstration at MWC 2019	Attendance, 5GCity demonstration at MWC 2019, utilizing the Barcelona pilot

4.2. NEC

NEC will contribute to the dissemination of the 5GCity project by producing publications of high-quality in international media like peer reviewed magazines and journals including special issues in journals (ACM SIGCOMM, IEEE INFOCOM, ACM CONEXT, USENIX ATC, SOSP, OSDI, HoCloud): NEC expects submissions to the previously mentioned in the next 6 months.

NEC is also very active in the XEN community and has been approved for creating a XEN subproject for Unicore, under the auspices of the Linux Foundation. NEC is still working out the release schedule (it includes PR and interviews with journalists), but it should be done before the end of November.

Table 4: NEC planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
IEEE HPSR	July 2018	Unicore Hackathon (co-hosted)	http://hpsr2018.ieee-hpsr.org/
Xen Summit	2018 (tbd)	Unicore presentation (Unicore is about to become a Xen sub- project)	Not Available
Linuxcon 2018	tbd	Unicore presentation	Not Available
Linaro conference 2018	tbd	Unicore presentation	Not Available

4.3. VOSYS

VOSYS will participate in the dissemination activities for the 5GCity via the contributions into different Open Source communities in which they have an active presence and that are relevant for the objectives of the project. These selected communities are the Linux KVM community, the QEMU developers' community, the OPNFV standardization project, and the Open Data Plane (ODP) project.

VOSYS sees also as an important way of dissemination, the participation in industry events as for example the Interop Tokyo 2018.

And lastly, VOSYS will also contribute to the dissemination of the project by producing publications of high-quality in scientific magazines, journals, and conferences as for example the IEEE BMSB 2018

Table 5: VOSYS planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
Interop 2018 - Tokyo	June 2018	Booth and demonstration	Attendance, Interop 2018 in Tokyo
IEEE BMSB 2018 - Valencia	June 2018	Technical paper presentation	Authors

4.4. RTV

RTV will contribute to the dissemination activities by having presence in the biggest exhibitions in Barcelona as the Mobile World Congress and the Smart City Congress. There, RTV will have an active participation bringing staff and producing informative videos and brochures. On top of that RTV will publish at least one press release per year (in national and international media) and will add a reference and a summary of the project in the Retevisión's corporate website <https://www.cellnextelecom.com/proyectos/>

RTV will also organize a Major workshop at Retevisión HQ in Barcelona to showcase major project achievements, and also a minor workshop to showcase the project and its achievements. The location for the latter is unknown at the time of writing, but will be decided in the second period.

Table 6: RTV planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
Smart City Expo 2017 - Barcelona	November 2017	Booth at the Smart City Expo, Project description in video world.	Attendance and presentation.
MWC 2018 - Barcelona	February 2018	Booth at the MWC, Project presentation. Outcomes shown in video panel.	Attendance and NH architecture showcasing, also presenting with IMI, Accelleran and i2Cat.
Smart City Expo 2018 - Barcelona	November 2018	Booth at the Smart City Expo, Project description in video world.	Attendance and presentation.
MWC 2019 - Barcelona	February 2019	Booth at the MWC, Project presentation. Outcomes shown in video panel.	Attendance and NH use case demonstration.

4.5. PRISMTECH

PrismTech will contribute to the dissemination objectives of the project through the following activities.

OpenFog Consortium. As an active member of the OpenFog Consortium we will:

- Ensure that the findings of the 5GCity project are considered in the definition of the OpenFog architecture;
- Ensure that the relevant reflections and requirements identified within the OpenFog consortium are considered as part of the 5GCity project;
- Promote OpenFog Test Beds based on the platform resulting from the 5GCity project.

This activity will span across P1 and P2.

Talks and Keynotes. As a result of our recognized role of thought leaders in Fog Computing we are regularly invited to deliver keynotes and talks at International Conferences and Industry events, such as the MWC, Edge Computing Conference, Fog World, etc. Prismtech will leverage this regular communication activity to promote 5GCity and share the discoveries of the project. This activity will span across P1 and P2.

Publications. Prismtech contribute regularly to industry-specific journals and technology publications. Likewise, we regularly publish our research on peer-reviewed Journal and Conferences. We will use this regular activity to share the main research results from the 5GCity project. This begin toward the end P1 span across P2.

Open Source. Prismtech runs several Open Source projects related to IoT and Fog Computing, some of these are hosted as part of the Eclipse IoT ecosystem. We will leverage this ecosystem to popularize the open source created by the 5GCity project. This activity will be executed whenever new software is released as Open Source by any of the 5G members.

4.6. UNIBRIS / BiO

UNIBRIS will contribute to the dissemination activities, by producing publications of high-quality results in international media like peer reviewed magazines and journals including special issues in journals (e.g., ECOC 2018, OFC 2019, IEEE Communication Magazine etc.). On these articles, the objective will be to present results from preliminary studies and experiments obtained from the planning, deployment and demonstration phases of the use cases on Bristol, Lucca and Barcelona.

On the publishing front UNIBRIS also plans to produce two white papers highlighting 5G City innovations in Bristol, both as seed for a magazine article. Both will be used later on as a seed for a magazine article.

UNIBRIS will also contribute to the dissemination of 5GCity by interacting with the Open Networking Foundation (ONF) community, responsible for working on standardizing the interfaces that will be needed by the project

Table 7: UNIBRIS/BiO planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
5G UK Winter Festival	March 2018	Presentation and dissemination by using posters and talk about 5G City project.	To be provided
ECOC 2018	September 2018	Paper submission for presentation	http://www.ecoc2018.org/
SDN NFV World Congress (NFV+SDN & Automation for 5G, Transport & Cloud)	October 2018	Posters promoting 5G City preliminary results.	https://www.layer123.com/sdn-register/
IEEE Communication Magazine	Open 2018	Submit an article about 5G and MEC/FOG	Not Available
OFC 2019	March 2019	Paper submission for presentation	http://www.ofcconference.org/en-us/home/?utm_source=researchbib
IEEE ICTON 2019	July 2019	Paper submission for presentation	
IEEE/OSA Scientific Journal	Open 2019	Article extending all conference papers presented.	https://www.osapublishing.org
Open Network Foundation (ONF) standardization group	Open 2019	Interactions for standardization of interfaces.	https://www.opennetworking.org/events/

4.7. NEXTWORKS

NEXTWORKS will contribute to the dissemination objectives from 5GCity by producing publications of high-quality results in local, national and international media. A part from the publications, NEXTWORKS will participate in international events as the SDN/NFV World Congress, Softnetworking or the EuCNC

Table 8: NEXTWORKS planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
SDN/NFV World Congress		Submission of a paper	https://www.layer123.com/sdn
Softnetworking 2018	February 2018	Submission of a paper	https://www.iaria.org/conferences2018/SOFTNETWORKING18.html
EuCNC	June 2018	Submission of a paper	Not Available

4.8. LUCCA

Municipality of Lucca will contribute to the dissemination objectives of the 5GCity project by disseminating the results of the validated LUCCA use case on smart environment video surveillance within the networks of towns and municipalities on which LUCCA participates, during the life span of the project. For that, the municipality of Lucca will use direct mailings, meetings, web publications, press conferences targeting the networks of towns and municipalities on which LUCCA participates e.g. ANCI, National Association of Italian Municipalities, LTA, Logical Town Association with whom there are already strong links between the city of Lucca and the other associated and interested towns;

Municipality of Lucca, will also contribute to the dissemination activities by participating in at least two workshops at National/International events gathering cities on environmental issues. The first one will during the fall of 2018 and the second one will be sometimes in 2019.

Table 9: LUCCA planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
POLIS annual Conference, Brussels	Fall 2018	Booth and presentation	https://www.polisnetwork.eu
European Committee of the regions, Brussels	Open 2019	Press conference and presentation	http://cor.europa.eu/en

4.9. ITL

Italtel contribution to the dissemination activities will be divided in three main fronts.

Firstly, organizing at least one dissemination event, in one municipality among Milan-Turin-Palermo, about Smart City and 5G-based services features and participating in at least one European national industry event about Smart City. Secondly publishing at publications of high-quality results in ICT local/national/international conferences and media. And lastly, using the traditional Italtel communication channels (press, video, and blogs) and Social Media Channels (Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, LinkedIn) to promote 5GCity achievements and future events.

Table 10: ITL planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
Cisco Live Event - Barcelona	January 2018	Participation at the event	Not Available
Mobile World Congress – Barcelona	February 2018	Participation at the event	Not Available

4.10. IMI

IMI will contribute to the dissemination of the 5GCity project by organizing two workshops and a hackathon in Barcelona. The workshops will be organized, one during the Smart City Expo 2018 and it will be about 5G-enabled cities and the other will be organized and hosted during the MWC 2019 and it will use Barcelona’s pilot to demonstrate the work done on 5GCity project. On a similar manner, IMI will organize a city hackathon to present the 5GCity pilot and open it to the relevant stakeholders.

On another front, IMI will help by integrating project results in several standardization bodies as:

- as members in AENOR CTN 178 Committee focused on Smart Cities and City Protocol Society
- as members in City Networks as EUROCITIES, Major Cities of Europe or WeGo;
- as support of AENOR1 and CPS Delegations in ITU and ISO (Sustainable Communities)

Table 11: IMI planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
SESIAD (Spain Government) UNE (Standardization Bodies)	September 2017	Face to face meeting	Not Available
Smart City Expo '17 - Barcelona	November 2017	Booth at the Smart City Expo, managing of project presentation. Design of information panels.	http://www.smartcityexpo.com/ca/home
Smart City Expo '18 - Barcelona	November 2018	Booth at the Smart City Expo, managing	http://www.smartcityexpo.com/ca/home

		of project presentation. Design of information panels.	
Smart City Expo '19 - Barcelona	November 2019	Booth at the Smart City Expo, managing of project presentation. Design of information panels.	http://www.smartcityexpo.com/ca/home

4.11. MOG

MOG will contribute to the dissemination activities required for the 5GCity project, participating as an exhibitor in the world leading events of the broadcasting sector: NAB, IBC, Interbee, and SET. MOG will also be doing demonstrations of the 5GCity technologies, pilots and use cases at two relevant European events (at least) and at the relevant standardization forums such as the Society of Motion Pictures Engineers (SMPTE)

Table 12: MOG planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
IBC 2018 - Amsterdam	September 2018	Booth (Use case demonstration at IBC 2018)	Attendance, IBC expo.
NAB 2019 - Los Angeles	April 2019	Booth (Use case demonstration at NAB 2019)	Attendance, NAB expo.

4.12. H3G

H3G will disseminate the 5GCity innovations in a few standardization bodies within Europe and worldwide, as ITU-T, ITU-R, CEI to better understand the strategic impacts on the project evolution. Besides that, H3G will also focus on Fireworks Group outcome.

Other activities in which H3G will participate, will be the publishing of a yearly press release and the production of brochures.

Lastly, H3G will disseminate the 5GCity innovations, findings and solutions to the main telecommunication stakeholders involved. H3G will explore in 5GCity the sustainability of new solutions from technical and economic perspective so as to have a complete vision of all opportunities for a huge range of fixed-line and mobile telephony integrated solutions; in particular, H3G will be involved in the mobile networks evolution path focused on 5G technologies; according to this, H3G plans to disseminate 5GCity's results by means of internal and external communications; in particular, results will be disseminated through internal newsletter and other materials to inform the involved departments (Technology Network/IT and Market), web site.

Table 13: H3G planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
Fireworks: Amsterdam Meeting # 52 (Sep 27nd-28t)	September 2017	Activities Project presentation	Presentation @ Fireworks board

4.13. RAI

RAI contributions to the dissemination activities for the 5GCity project will be focusing on demonstrating the 5GCity Media & Entertainment use case in relevant events organized by the consortium, together with the relevant cities hosting the Media & Entertainment scenario.

Using its relevant position as a national broadcaster, RAI will do dissemination of the project in organizations and technical bodies such as DVB (Digital Video Broadcasting) and EBU. It will also add a summary of the project at the corporate website (crit.rai.it)

Lastly RAI plans to produce publications of high-quality results in scientific magazines, journals, conferences and workshops.

Table 14: RAI planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
European Digital Forum and UHD 4K Summit - Lucca	June 2018	Presentation and demo area	Not Available
IBC 2018 - Amsterdam	September 2018	5G Media Paper	Not Available
EBU Forecast 2018	November 2018	Presentation	Not Available

4.14. UBIWHERE

UBIWHERE will participate to the dissemination activities of 5GCity by making the results of 5GCity visible through social media and networking at events such as MWC, Smart City Expo. UBIWHERE will also issue 2 press releases per year on the company's website.

They will also do dissemination through 5G-PPP and OASC towards other cities which UBIWHERE considers relevant for the goals of the project.

Table 15: UBIWHERE planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
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Salon des Maires 2017	November 2017	Small booth (Smart Lamppost) where 5GCITY's Use Cases will be quickly presented	Not Available
Smart City Expo World Congress	November 2017	Booth at the Smart City Expo, Smart pole concept and vision presentation.	Smart pole concept and prototype presentation. . Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) use case presentation.
MWC 2018 - Barcelona	February 2018	Probably a booth	Smart pole concept and prototype presentation. Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) use case presentation.
EuCNC 2018	June 2018	To be confirmed	Not Available
Smart City Expo World Congress 2018	November 2018	Probably a booth	Attendance, Smart City Expo 2018 in Barcelona

4.15. BTV

- 5GCity dissemination through internal media outlets (TV, Radio, and Internet platforms).
- Participation in Spanish media events: (i) TV Markets; (ii) Digital Festivals (FICOD); and (iii) TV and sectorial symposiums (Foro IA).

4.16. INC

INCITES participation on the dissemination activities for 5GCity will focus on publishing high-quality results in international media like peer reviewed magazines and journals including special issues in journals like:

- CTTE Conference (<http://www.ctte-conference.com/>)
- OFC COncference (<http://www.ofconference.org/>)
- Telecommunications Policy Journal (<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/telecommunications-policy>)
- IEEE Communications Magazine (<http://www.comsoc.org/commag>)
- EuCNC conference (<http://www.eucnc.eu/>)
- 5G PINE Workshop

INCITES plans also to promote and disseminate the project through the 5GPPP Societal and Vision Working Group.

Lastly INCITES will be using its website and social media accounts in twitter and LinkedIN to promote 5G city achievements and future events. Related to that, mention also that INCITES will be also working on the production of videos promoting the 5G city concept (the first was delivered on M1 of the project)

Table 16: INC planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
Production of a video highlighting the 5G City concept	June 2017	To be confirmed	Not Available
OFC	March 2018	Paper submitted for presentation	Presentation (if paper is accepted)
EuCNC	June 2018	Submission of a paper or/and organization of a workshop	Attendance, presentation, organization of a workshop
5G Pine workshop	September 2018	Submission of a paper	Presentation (if paper is accepted)
EuCNC	June 2019	Submission of a paper or/and organization of a workshop	Attendance, presentation, organization of a workshop

4.17. XLRN

XLRN will contribute to 5GCity dissemination activities by participating at the Small Cell Forum, and focusing there on the 5G, virtualization and multi-operator neutral host. XLRN will be also doing dissemination work about 5GCity project as a member of the Global TD-LTE Initiative during the GTI Workshops organized yearly, particularly the ones organized during MWC 2018 and 2019 in Barcelona. Similarly, they will be disseminating 5GCity project while participating at the SmartCity Expo World Congress.

XLRN will offer support for the workshops and pilots organized by other participants where Accelleran Small Cell technology is used.

Table 17: XLRN planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
Smart City Expo '17 - Barcelona	November 2017	Booth at the Smart City Expo, Small Cell integration in Barcelona Lamppost	Attendance, Smart City Expo 2017 in Barcelona
Small Cell World Summit Americas San Jose 2017	December 2017	Booth at the SCWS Americas 2017 with PR/panel related to 5GCity	Attendance, SCWS America 2017
MWC 2018 - Barcelona	February 2018	Booth at the MWC18 with PR/panel related to 5GCity	Attendance, MWC18
MWC 2019 - Barcelona	February 2019	Pilot demonstration at MWC 2019	Attendance, 5GCity demonstration at MWC 2019, utilizing the Barcelona pilot

4.18. CODI

CODI's considers essential to look for opportunities that can fuel visibility, stimulate the promotion through the media and the press; and that can build a strong networking and contact opportunities among the technological and scientific community at European and international level.

To help on that promotion, CODI will plan a demonstration of the 5GCity technology in a pilot to be hosted in the city of Lucca. CODI will also work on a workshop organization (European Digital Forum and UHD 4K Summit) in Lucca and Brussels in collaboration with Ultra HD Forum – SMPTE and integration analysis by EBU and DVB.

Lastly CODI plans to influence the UHD/4K contents proposal to be included into digital devices and TV/5G set.

Table 18: CODI planned activities

Activity (i.e.: workshop, paper, fair...)	Date/ Timeline	Description	Additional information (i.e.: Attendance or organization, links ...)
PE/Brussels	April 2018	5G Press Conference/Workshop	Not Available
BIT 2018 - Madrid	May 2018	5G Media Round Table	Not Available
4th F2F 5GCity - Lucca	June 2018	5GCity Consortium Meeting	Not Available
FED 2018 - Lucca	June 2018	5G Media Keynote/Round Table/Demo Area	Not Available
5GWorld - London	June 2018	5G Media Keynote/Round Table/Demo Area	Not Available
IBC 2018 - Amsterdam	September 2018	5G Media Paper	Not Available
4KSummit 2018 - Malaga	November 2018	5G Media Keynote/Round Table/	Not Available

5. Impact Indicators and reporting

5.1. Impact indicators

The set of KPI defined in the 5GCity project will help when measuring the success of the dissemination activities. This section intends to review the foreseen impact of the dissemination plan with the KPI.

- **Open Source Contributions:** 5GCity project will contribute to different Open Source communities (and the goal for this particular item is to have at least two contributions accepted within the project's lifetime. The project will target some principal Open Source contributions which will be addressed during the second period once the project has advanced its technical development (see section 3.1)
- **Pilots and proof of concepts (PoC's):** For measuring the success on the pilots and PoCs, it was agreed that there has to be a PoC pilot deployed by every city and also a common pilot replicated in the three cities. This will be one of the main outputs of the project and it is foreseen the achievement of this KPI. Furthermore, the project will also aim for one pilot demonstration at MWC.
- **Contribution to standards:** 5GCity will be making contributions to OpenFog, ETSI MEC and ETSI NFV consortiums (more will be analyzed in the WP6 as a part of the standardization task). The goal for this activity is to have at least two contributions accepted.
- **Industry events and ad-hoc meetings:** 5GCity consortium has been tasked with organizing at least 2 workshops and to participate in at least 2 industry events per year. As has been specified in the list of events (see section 3.11) the project will be present in more than two industrial events every year. One of the two workshops have been already identified and the second one will be targeted during the second period of the project.
- **Publications:** 5GCity wants to be present in the industry and the scientific communities and also on the events organized by EU, and for that the following KPI have been set, to ensure that the project reaches the objective.
 - **Industry related Publications:** at least 5 publications
 - **Scientific Publications:** at least 15 publications
 - **EU events Publications:** at least a yearly publication in some of the EU organized events

Already 12 highly relevant workshops and congresses have been identified as suitable for submitting papers and proceedings. A close follow-up of the status of these papers will be done to ensure the achievement of this KPI.

- Apart from publications, the project will also target at least two white papers.
- **Web site, social networks, and press releases:** 5GCity will setup a Public website, publish 2 newsletters per year and use a social networking tool. The project has already launched a Website is actively using social networking and as specified in section 3.7 is planning to launch a newsletter every quarter from month 9 onwards.

5.2. Reporting

In order to track and plan dissemination activities, event and publication tracking methodology has been introduced. The partners will report, on a monthly basis, both the foreseen dissemination opportunities of the project, the attendance to events as well as the publications related with the project. In addition to the

regular information of the events (where it took place, who assisted, contributions, etc.), the partners are requested to report about the number and kind of audience and the future outcomes and impact of the activity (publications, contacts, press releases.)

6. Conclusions

The dissemination and communication plan defines who the stakeholders will be (section 1), what communication tools are used to promote the dissemination actions (section 2), what specific events and channels are used to disseminate the project (section 3), the commitments of the different partners (section 4) and in last place how the dissemination and communication strategy aligns with the compromises defined in the ECGA (section 5).

All in all, the project has established an initial dissemination plan to coordinate the efforts of the consortium in an effective and coherent approach such that the dissemination objectives of the project are ensured. The plan presented in this document is subject to update depending upon the progress of the project, in an adaptive way, to make sure dissemination goals are achieved.

Abbreviations and Definitions

6.1. Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MST	Management Team
PC	Project Coordinator
PMO	Project Management Office
PO	Project Officer
TB	Technical Board
TC	Technical Coordinator
IM	Innovation Manager
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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